

Community Needs Assessment of Barangay Pinsao Proper: Basis for Sustainable Health, Peace, and Order Programs

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Abstract. The availability of basic health services to the constituents and the promotion of peace and order in the Barangay are among the primary indicators of an inclusive and healthy community. In Baguio City, Barangay Pinsao Proper is among the barangays that continue to face difficulties in addressing the concerns of health, peace, and order. Using qualitative research, this study sought to determine the perceived needs and challenges encountered by community members. Data was gathered from official barangay records and eighteen (18) community members who voluntarily participated in a focus group interview. A lack of protective field gear, parental difficulties, mental health gaps, an inadequately equipped barangay clinic, and the requirement for frequent Basic Life Support (BLS) training were among the major issues identified by thematic analysis. Cultural tensions, youth-related violence, and the barangay authorities' limited ability to resolve conflicts were the main causes of peace and order problems. The findings aided in the development of the Pinsao Project – a three (3) year development plan program for the Barangay to be implemented by the University of Baguio. The findings of the study serve as a basis for local development initiatives and academic community engagements toward the attainment of an inclusive community.

Introduction

Barangay Pinsao Proper, located in Baguio City, is among the communities grappling with pressing concerns related to health services and peace and order. A preliminary agreement among the University of Baguio, Barangay Pinsao Proper, and the City Social Welfare and Development Office in 2024 highlighted the need for a comprehensive needs assessment to serve as the foundation for sustainable outreach initiatives (Memorandum of Agreement, 2024). The initiative aligns with the University's U.B. CARES program, which promotes social responsibility through structured interventions like Adopt-a-Barangay and other projects (University of Baguio, 2021). Despite previous projects, gaps remain in access to adequate medical services, mental health support, and peacekeeping capabilities, suggesting the need for targeted and evidence-based programs.

Globally and locally, literature underscores that health literacy, mental health support, and effective community peacekeeping are intertwined challenges in marginalized communities. Low health literacy is associated with higher healthcare costs, increased hospitalization, and poorer outcomes (Shahid et al., 2022; Pfizer, n.d.). Studies have shown that even where barangay clinics exist, underutilization persists due to shortages in medicines, equipment, and specialized services (Cananua-Labid et al., 2024). Simultaneously, mental health issues often remain unaddressed due to stigma, lack of resources, and absence of context-specific programs (Tuaf & Orkibi, 2025). On the aspect of peace and order, research by Metillo et al. (2022) and Nicor-Mangilimutan et al. (2020) highlights that barangay-level governance faces limitations, including insufficient training in conflict resolution and resource constraints, which hinder effective implementation of peacekeeping initiatives.

While community needs assessments are widely recognized tools for identifying local priorities, global reviews point to varying practices and a lack of consistency in linking identified needs to measurable program outcomes (Ravaghi et al.,

2023). Moreover, few studies in the Philippine context have closely examined the combined issues of health service gaps and peace and order in culturally diverse urban barangays. This study, therefore, addresses a clear research gap: developing an evidence-based, sustainable outreach program rooted in a systematic assessment of community needs in Barangay Pinsao Proper. Hence, this study addresses the following objectives:

1. To identify the felt needs of the community members regarding Health, Peace, and Order;
2. To identify the challenges encountered by the community members on Health, Peace, and Order.
3. To develop a sustainable community outreach program focusing on health promotion and enhancing peace and order.

Literature Review

Role of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Sustainable Community Development

Community outreach and services have long been essential to enhancing the quality of life in marginalized and underserved communities. Delivered by universities, government agencies, and non-governmental organizations, these programs foster well-being, empowerment, and inclusive development (Betuin et al., 2023; Nicolaides & Austin, 2022). In the Philippine context, the role of higher education institutions (HEIs) extends beyond teaching and research; it embraces community engagement as a moral responsibility (Alarte, 2022). Through these extension services, HEIs provide sustainable and responsive interventions addressing real needs identified by communities themselves.

The long-term viability of a society is deeply tied to the harmonious development of economic and environmental well-being, social justice promotion, and participation of the community in the decision-making processes. With that, it is a global truth that a university has an important role to play in responding to a range of societal needs (Nicolaides & Austin, 2022) through its community extension programs. In the Philippines, the said role goes beyond the traditional academic functions of an institution. It morally adheres to every institution's four-fold function, to wit: instruction, research, extension, and linkages. As an environment for quality assessment, higher educational institutions were then required to provide community services (Alarte, 2022). This implies that providing extension programs to the community fosters mutual learning, empowerment, and sustainable development through collaborative engagement and resource sharing.

Community Health Literacy and Health Outcomes

On Community Health issues, inadequate health literacy is recognized as a stronger predictor of poor health than factors like age, income, education level, or race (Shahid, 2022). This results in higher healthcare expenses, increased use of inpatient and emergency services, and poorer health outcomes. Consequently, addressing health literacy gaps through education, improved communication strategies, and tailored interventions is crucial to promoting better health outcomes and well-being within communities (Pfizer, n.d).

Some studies have shown that community health needs assessment is used widely by different users and across different settings. However, these studies varied widely in terms of purpose, process, and methods of conducting community health needs assessment. Furthermore, the extent to which an asset-based approach is used is unclear, beyond the inclusion in guidance and recommendations. Thus, to support national or local decision-makers to make informed choices about the scope, tools, methods, and use of community health needs and assets assessment, this scoping review of the literature aimed at 1) Providing conceptual clarity on community health needs and assets assessment, 2) Determining for what purpose and with what methods community health needs and assets assessment are used globally, 3) Drawing the lessons learned from previous experience with community health needs and assets assessment: what works in what context and under what conditions, 4) Documenting evidence of impact of community health needs and assets assessment, 5) Consolidating tools and methods used to collect evidence/data underpinning community health needs and assets assessment processes. (Ravaghi et al 2023).

With this, the community health assessment will give an overview of the community's current health status, needs, and issues. This information can help develop a community health improvement plan by justifying how and where resources should be allocated to best meet community needs in relevance to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention.

Rayan-Gharra et al. (2022) conducted a community health needs assessment that revealed that some impact of social determinants on health status and outcomes has been widely established. However, the study showed that it is recognized that health systems' ability to address community health needs may be limited. To better understand the interrelation between social determinants of health and health outcomes, health systems need to understand the health concerns and needs of populations.

Still on Community Health issues, Adler (2021) mentioned in his study "The Epistemological Challenge of Truth Subversion to the Liberal International Order" that Populist leaders' use of truth-subversion tactics to gain political dominance is a major source of the strain that the Liberal International Order (LIO) is currently under. False speak (blatant lying to undermine the notion of facts), doublespeak (intended internal inconsistencies in speech to undermine reason), and flooding (the release of numerous messages into the public domain to confuse) are examples of truth subversion techniques. The study only implies that truth subversion undermines epistemic security, or the sense of safety and order that arises from individuals and organizations having a similar knowledge of reality. It seeks to undermine liberal truth principles and practices and favors irrational assertions above beliefs supported by facts.

Peace, Order, and Barangay-Level Governance

On the other hand, securing the peace and safety of individuals is crucial for sustaining economic progress, societal harmony, and political stability. At the barangay level, barangay officials play a crucial role in maintaining peace and order in the community. According to Metillo et al. (2022), the elements of promoting peace and order in the barangays involve spreading ordinances effectively, maintaining relationships, resolving issues promptly, making beneficial agreements, and ensuring barangay officials approach disputes positively. Similarly, the study of Nicor-Mangilimutan (2020) evaluated the implementation of the Community Peace and Order and Public Safety Program in Negros Occidental, Philippines, focusing on crime prevention, anti-illegal drugs, public safety, and enforcement of ordinances. Their study revealed that the implementation of the POPS program is hindered by various challenges, such as poor access in geographically isolated areas, a lack of rescue equipment, and financial constraints affecting program expectations. Also, their study revealed that beneficial seminars shall be conducted, empower the residents to report on illegal drugs, intensify monitoring efforts, disseminate local ordinances effectively, and create enforcement teams to enhance program implementation. Therefore, the role of HEIs in mitigating community health and peace and order issues through research and development is needed to address healthcare issues in the community.

On the issues of peace and order according to Juharni. Et.al (2024) in their research titled "The Implementation of Community Policing Policies in the Era of the Industrial Revolution 4.0 to Prevent Social Conflict in the Maros Resort Police Area". The results showed that the implementation of the role of community policing in the era of the Industrial Revolution to prevent social conflict in the context of the realization is to optimize problem mapping (scanning) to prevent social conflict and increase public awareness of the importance of maintaining security, order in various activities carried out by the police to support the Community Policing program.

More and more people believe that environmental management and development should aim for sustainability. Sustainability can be defined broadly or narrowly and the meaning of the term is strongly dependent on the context in which it is applied and on whether its use is based on a social, economic, or ecological perspective. This, research study entitled "Sustainable community development through sport and events: A conceptual framework for Sport-for-Development projects" by Nico Schulenkorf (2012) it was concluded that in disadvantaged and/or divided societies, Sport-for-Development projects have been staged to contribute to intergroup togetherness, inclusive social change and local capacity building within and between communities.

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a qualitative-descriptive research design incorporating a group interview approach and document analysis to assess the needs of the Barangay. This approach allowed the researchers to conduct an in-depth exploration of the community's needs related to health, peace, and order.

Participants of the Study

This study involved eighteen (18) representatives from different sectors in Barangay Pinsao Proper, Baguio City. The researchers employed convenient random sampling in conducting the study due to practical, logistical, and contextual considerations inherent in community-based research. Specifically, the study was carried out in a natural community setting where time constraints, accessibility of respondents, and availability during the data collection period were significant factors. Convenient sampling allowed the researchers to efficiently reach participants who were readily accessible and willing to participate, thereby ensuring timely data collection without disrupting community activities.

Instrumentation and Data Gathering Process

This study utilized a focus group interview to delve further into the needs of the community in terms of Health and Peace & Order. The interview guide has four general themes/categories to base on the objectives of this study, to wit: (1) Identification of problems related to health and peace and order (2) Existing programs/efforts of the barangay related to health and peace and order (3) Challenges encountered to the implementation of existing programs, and (4) other possible programs/activities that the barangay can do. Each category has specific open-ended questions. Also, a document analysis was utilized during the conduct of the study. The researchers reviewed accessible documents as offered by the Barangay, such as the Barangay Residence Assessment Monitoring Sheet (BRAMS) and Barangay Development Plan (BDP). With the permission of the participants, a voice recorder/cell phone was also used to record the interview.

The group interview was conducted at the Pinsao Proper Barangay Hall, as this was the most convenient venue for the interview, as suggested by the Punong Barangay. The participants were also invited to the Barangay, and they joined voluntarily. On the other hand, there are target participants who were also invited but opted not to join, and the researchers respected their decision. The said data-gathering procedure was done synchronously with the two research groups focusing on different aspects of the barangay.

Data Analysis

Audio recording was carefully transcribed, and transcriptions were cross-checked against the original audio recording to ensure that there was no missing information. Qualitative data were analyzed using a thematic analysis following Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-phase framework: familiarization, initial coding, theme development, review, definition, and reporting. Codes were clustered into broader themes in relation to health, peace, and order needs of the community. A document analysis was also utilized to support the primary data collected by the researchers.

Research Ethics

This study adhered to the ethical research guidelines to ensure that the rights and dignity of the participants were protected. This study also upheld autonomy and beneficence throughout the study. Only upon acquiring approval from the university as well as the Punong Barangay did the researchers begin the administration of the interview. All data collected was treated with utmost confidentiality. Personal information of the participants was not disclosed in any part of the study. All collected data, such as recorded interviews and transcripts, were uploaded to Google Drive and were only accessible to the researchers. This study also ensures that the data will be disposed of properly by deleting all the files after the study has been completed and presented to a research platform.

Disclosure of the usage of Artificial Intelligence

The researchers declared that this research was assisted by ChatGPT (free version), which was used in translating the transcribed interviews (from Ilocano/Tagalog to English) and improving the readability of the paper. All generated content from ChatGPT was critically reviewed by the researchers, and human oversight was observed to maintain the accuracy of the data as well as the integrity of the researchers. Also, Consensus AI was utilized in this study to gather relevant works of literature for corroboration.

Results and Discussion

Felt Needs of the Community Members on the Health Aspect

The participants shared similar felt needs in terms of the Health aspect. These are the immediate needs as perceived by the participants in the community. Based on the interviews conducted, there are six (6) identified needs that the participants have emphasized as imperative to improving the well-being of Barangay Pinsao Proper residents such as; a) Well-equipped barangay clinic with sufficient medical supplies, b) Provision of protective gear, and cleaning materials to reduce health risks during field activities, c) Community involvement in sanitation programs, d) Introduction of mental health seminars focused on youth, solo parents, and other community members, e) Counseling programs that focus on responsible parenting and child development, and f) Regular Basic Life Support (BLS) training for residents, especially PWDs.

Well-equipped Barangay Clinic with Sufficient Medical Supplies

This remains the main concern in the Barangay. According to Cananua-Labid (2024), the lack of basic medical necessities is a recurring issue in a barangay. Their study revealed that there is a demand from the community to improve facilities and provision of medical supplies in the Barangay to address the underutilization of the Barangay clinic. Similar to the study of

Labid et al. (2024), this study also revealed the need for a well-equipped barangay clinic that can provide a broader range of medical care, as identified by the participants. These services include the provision of medicines (for common illnesses such as cough, colds, and dengue), vaccines, and medical apparatus. On the availability of vaccines, P18 shared, “gaya nung..yung Flu vaccine atsaka yung one-time vaccine. Yun yung kulang na maibigay nila. Kasi kung mayroong pupunta na senior, sabihin nila na wala kami niyan ngayon, wala pa ngayon. So, yun ang mga kulang nila. Other medications, may kulang pa na gusto namin na maibigay din sa mga senior citizens” (Like the flu vaccine - those are things that they don't have. When a senior visits in, they are told that such is not still unavailable. As for other medications, there are still some shortages, and we also want to give those to the senior citizens.”.

This implies a gap in the services provided by the Barangay, especially in the provision of vaccines and medicines. According to UNICEF Philippines and the Department of Health, as cited by Cananua-Labid (2024), while vaccines are expected to be available at the Barangay level, concerns still remain in the delivery of service. Some medicines and vaccines are out of stock or unavailable when most needed.

On the availability of medical apparatus being used during home visits, the BNS volunteers voiced out the lack of medical apparatus when conducting home visits to check the newborn infants and their mothers. P17 and P16 noted that though there is a sphygmomanometer, it is too big to carry during house visits. They expressed a hope of being provided with a portable one. P16 said, “Sana (I hope) someone can provide us with the minor instrument (BP/Thermometer apparatus), so that if we are going to have our home visits, at least we have that minor instrument.” P17 added “meron naman yung ano pero malaki kasi. We need the portable one (We have one, but it's big. We need the portable one — a sphygmomanometer specifically for children)”.

This finding is consistent with similar studies conducted in other areas. This concern is supported by Reyes et al. (2023), who confirmed that poor working conditions and limited resources limit the Barangay Health Workers (BHW) in providing high-quality basic health care. Thus, this suggests the importance of strengthening logistical support for BHWs.

Provision of Protective Gear and Cleaning Materials to Reduce Health Risks During Field Activities

Waste segregation is an important aspect. Participants also shared that during clean-up drives in the Barangay, they no longer go down to the creeks due to safety concerns, specifically the dangers posed by leptospirosis and dengue. P15 shared, “Pero ngayon di na kami bumababa sa mga creek kasi nakakatakot. Dahil sa leptospirosis at dengue. dati -dati noon, bumababa kami sa creek, pero ngayon natatakot na kami (But now, we no longer go down to the creeks because we are afraid of leptospirosis and dengue. Before, we went down to the creek, but now we're afraid)”. P12 also agreed that there are two barangay officials from other barangays who died because of leptospirosis during a dengue drive. This increases fear among health workers and volunteers, who no longer engage in fieldwork as they did before. P14 revealed “Dahil may namatay na ngay na dalawang Kagawad. Ongoing noon ang simultaneous na dengue drive, eh binaba niya yun. Dalawa sila. Eh kasama ko sila sa Federation ng Baguio. (Two barangay officials have already passed away in the course of a one-time dengue drive. One of them went down to the location as part of the operation. There were two of them involved, both of whom were my colleagues in the Baguio Federation.”

According to Hartigan-Go et al. (2023), barangay health workers faced risks of acquiring leptospirosis due to exposure to floodwaters and limited protective equipment. The same concern is now felt by the Barangay volunteers who are hesitant to do fieldwork due to the perceived health risks. When active barangay volunteers and BHWs begin to withdraw from clean-up drives due to safety concerns, this will create a significant gap in the public health response system. If this issue remains unaddressed, this may lead to a more serious problem, such as long-term disengagement of the volunteers and a higher incidence of outbreaks. This finding is supported by existing literature, which emphasizes that working with the dengue virus requires strict biosafety precautions due to the potential risk of exposure. These global standards highlight the need for protective measures to ensure the safety of individuals involved in environments where dengue transmission is possible (Le & Blacksell, 2025).

Community Involvement in Sanitation Programs

Solid waste management has become one of the most pressing environmental concerns of the Philippines at present (Camarillo & Bellotindos, 2021). The participation of the households is seen to be of paramount importance in managing the solid wastes they, in the first place, generate (Cabias et al., 2024). This study revealed similar recurring issues in the community that need attention. One of the participants mentioned that despite the recommended guidelines for the segregation of garbage, there is still low compliance from the community members. P13 said, “Sa garbage Ma'am, marami pa rin ang hindi nag-sesegregate, Ma'am (On garbage, there are still those who don't segregate garbage)”. P14 added “yung dapat lang sana ay yung mga nabubulok, ilagay sa isang supot. Hindi nila i-mi-mix doon sa ano, para malaman namin sana kung ano yun. Kung talagang nabubulok, mai-sesegregate. Gaya ng mga.. Uhm...nasisirang mga kanin, mga pinagbalatan ng

ano. Oo, dapat ilagay doon sa isang supot. Wag i-mimix dun sa isang basura (Ideally, the biodegradable trash must be kept in a separate trash bag. They should not mix it with other types of waste so that we can identify what it is. It should be placed in one bag)."

This situation reflects a common challenge in promoting sustainable sanitation, where low awareness and limited participation hinder implementation, as emphasized by Sofiyah et al. (2025), who stressed that community resistance and weak engagement can significantly limit the success of sanitation initiatives. This concern is also consistent with the findings of Cabilas et al. (2024), which present that waste disposal practices in Hugpa, Biliran, were low. Their study indicates a discrepancy in compliance of the community with waste management guidelines. On the other hand, Ancheta et al. (2020) pointed out that waste management requires a two-way process. It includes strict policy implementation from the City Government and the community approach led by the Barangay Chairman. Accordingly, it requires a strict political network, funds, and community participation.

Introduction Of Mental Health Seminars Focused on Youth, Solo Parents, And Other Community Members

Concerns about mental health among youth are increasingly acknowledged as one of the major health concerns in the Philippines. Since 2015, psychological distress among Filipino adolescents has doubled, with around 27.8% of Filipino students experiencing psychological distress (Mallari and Peltzer, 2025). In the course of the interview, P2 brought up an important but commonly neglected concern among the community members - "mental health. They are unaware of how to handle their emotions". He pointed out that the youth seem to mishandle the educational issues and rivalry. Furthermore, these events were said to be motivated by family issues, academic stress, and interpersonal rivalries, which most young people find difficult to cope with appropriately. The pressure to live up to family expectations leads to breakdowns, P2 said, "Due to family issues and educational issues or rivalries, for whatever reason, they seem to mishandle it. And take the arguments upon themselves. For me, rivalry is regarding education. The expectations from parents". Furthermore, from P2's point of view, bipolar disorder and personality disorders are said to be common among all people in general, which highlights the need for continuous mental health interventions.

This finding confirms the research of Dewangan et al. (2023), who mentioned that academic stress influences the mental health of adolescents, with factors like academic demands, competitive environments, and parental expectations playing a role. Similarly, Xu et al. (2023) found that when an adolescent receives a high level of academic pressure from their parents, their mental health problems suffer. On the other hand, those adolescents with low levels of academic pressure tend to have fewer mental health problems.

Moreover, P9 highlighted the situation of solo parents, sharing an experience in which a mother cannot handle her children because she is experiencing emotional distress. P9 voiced, "Gaya nung isang solo parent, she doesn't know how to handle her children. I don't know what the problem is. Nagrebelde yung mga bata. Every time we have a meeting, instead yung concern ang paguusapan, yung mga anak na niya ang paguusapan (Like a solo parent who appears to have trouble handling her children. I don't know exactly why the problem exists, but the children are now rebellious. During every meeting, rather than discussing the real agenda or concerns of the community, the conversation tends to revolve around her children." In response, they suggested that she be counseled by the DSWD, reflecting on the need to link emotionally troubled individuals with expert services.

Furthermore, P4 shared her insights about solo parenting, particularly for mothers. Accordingly, when the mother herself lacks emotional support, she cannot give the same to her children. She said "para kenyak anya.ni mother ah, nu kaspangarigan, awan ngay ti pagalaan na ti emotional support, isu haan na ngay nga masuporta anak na emotionally kasi haan na nga maritna ti emotional support isu haan nan ga maioffer ken ni anak na, syempre jay anak na piman, ag seek piman ti sabali (For me, for example a mother who lacks emotional support cannot give emotional support to her children because she cannot feel it. In return, her child will start seeking emotional support somewhere)".

The respondent noted that peer pressure becomes a dominant force in the child's behavior, approximating that around 60% of such influence may be negative. Because emotional needs are not met at home, children become more susceptible to unhealthy peer relationships, which ultimately manifest in their actions and attitudes. These behavioral problems often come back to haunt the parent, causing self-doubt: "Usto ba jay ar-aramidek as a parent? (Am I doing the right thing as a parent?)."

P2 agreed to this as he viewed that "children of solo parents in non-nuclear formats lack emotional support from their parents. This can also lead to much more disorder, as there are times when, somehow, they are into illegal substances that lead to substance abuse. Either in their current or older years. As we are not trained to handle our emotions."

On the other hand, P8, who is a solo parent herself, negated the claims of P9, in which she expressed that women are not less capable of raising their children. She underscores the fact that she can take care of her children. She also argued that the aggressive behavior of a child might be the result of how the parent treats his/her child. She also acknowledged that internal family issues and external social forces, such as his/her peers, can be a part of a child's behavior. P9 said, "Cause nu solo parent ka...so I so I don't know..the way the parent nga ikasta na ti anak na isu nga agrebrelde isuna...or it's true nga naengganyo isuna ti friends na, kasjay ("Because if you're a single parent... I don't know, but maybe the parent is the one who causes the child to be rebellious. Or it might be that the child was also affected by their peers—that's just the way it goes sometimes."

According to D'Onoforio & Emery (2019), parental separation is related to high risk for children's mental health problems, including academic difficulties, disruptive behaviors, and depressed mood. Children's deviant behavior is attributed to two factors: unestablished and ineffective communication and disappointment with the family's situation (Putri and Yunita, 2024). Children whose emotional needs are not met at home usually seek emotional support from their peers (Kwon et al., 2024). Seeking out emotional support from peers may have positive and negative effects on their behavior. When a child builds and finds good friends, positive effects include improved well-being and social skills as well as resilience. However, real challenges occur when children are exposed to negative behaviors. This suggests that initial interventions shall begin with proper communication between parents and their children to address the emotional needs of the latter and mitigate the risk of deviant behavior among children.

When asked what programs are needed in the community, one participant shared that they need stress management as well as anger management seminars. P4 shared, "Actually po, dito mismo sa loob ng Barangay because kami ang nag-absorb ng mga issues sa labas. Dapat magkaroon ng program for that, unahin nyo kaming mga nasa barangay. We need that. Totoo po yun ("Actually, I think it should begin right here in the barangay because we are the ones who soak up the problems from the outside. There has to be a program for that—begin with us who are in the barangay. We need it. That's true." P4 also revealed her reflection regarding the emotional burden that she has experienced in handling barangay cases, particularly in her early years of service. She admitted that such cases would bother her even in her dreams as a result of deep empathy towards the parties concerned. She said, "I will have to admit that when I was still new here...yung handling of cases, pati sa panaginip ko sumasagi siya (I will have to admit that when I was still new here, the handling of cases would even bother me even in my dreams)". However, she also claimed that she became immune to constant exposure. To cope, they used humor or jokes while handling complaints. Further, she also stressed empathy to the participants, "in handling cases, mahirap resolbahin kung hindin mo nararamdaman yung bawat isa (In handling cases, (cases are difficult to resolve if you don't empathize with the parties involved).

P4 and P5 also expressed hope that seminars regarding stress and anger management and gender sensitivity would be pursued. He said, "Sana magtuloy tuloy po tulad ng mga gender sensitivity seminars, stress management (I hope that seminars such on gender sensitivity and stress management would be pursued). As such, these respondents saw the benefit of such programs in assisting both barangay officials and residents with emotional and interpersonal issues at the community level more effectively. As P5 expressed, "We cannot pour from an empty vessel".

Participants even shared an ideal seminar for them. P9 mentioned, "Stress management..seminars. Ngem jay adda ti active engagement ti tattao. Gamin nu seminars lang, agtogaw da lang. awan ti ag attend (Seminars on stress management. But there should be an active engagement from the attendees. Because if it is only a (typical) seminar, they will only sit there, no one will attend)". Such plain sitting usually serves as mere compliance from the people and will not have a meaningful impact. The participants added that for the programs to succeed, they should be specially designed to actively engage the people, rather than a lecture-type mode of seminars.

These reflections reinforce the importance of what the World Health Organization and Tuaf (2025) described as community-based rehabilitation (CBR)—a strategy designed to support recovery, emotional regulation, and social inclusion for people with mental health concerns. CBR emphasizes the need for accessible, context-specific interventions at the community level to address these rising concerns effectively. These findings align with the study of Deguma (2025), which explores mental health among informal caregivers in the Philippines. Their study revealed that the majority of their respondents experience struggle in managing their stress, which affects their ability to provide the best care for others. Thus, this can be addressed through targeted education, training programs, and accessible resources, thereby improving outcomes for all involved (Deguma, 2025).

Counseling Programs That Focus on Responsible Parenting and Child Development

Apart from the capacity-building programs that the participants have envisioned, responsible parenthood appears to be a relevant topic that needs to be addressed in the Barangay. The advent of technology affects even the relationship between family members. The reliance on smartphones by parents to calm their child has been the trend nowadays. As such, this may lead to reduced parent-child interaction. P2 shared, "For me, a lack of attention to the child, especially when they have

relied on using digital sources. You know those times when you are in the restaurant, and the child starts crying. Don't you notice that from hushing the child to giving them a cellphone? It is the lack of attention to the child." P6 affirmed while everyone in the room nodded, "It is still on the parents." This led to a unanimous suggestion among the participants that there should be programs to be implemented regarding child and parent counselling.

In addition, an interesting point of view from P2 was raised when he shared, "All of our problems came from the Pandemic. The strongest muscle in our body went to our jaw from our tongue". Interestingly, P6 also shared her observation when she was on a jeepney, she said, "This lady was sitting in a jeep, she was doing like this (acting like playing with her phone), as well as sleeping. And I said Why is she doing this and then sleeping. (laughs) nasanay na (She had probably gotten used to it). Nasabi ko bakit kaya ganun, nasanay na yung kamay niya (I wondered if her hands had simply gotten used to the action). Throughout the conversation, P5 also shared, "Tayo ngayon ano eh... magkakatabi tayo pero hindi nag-uusap. Meron kaming nakainan noon na resto, ang laki-laki ng sign, "Sorry, we don't have WI-FI here. We talk." Ang ganda. Kasi kakain nga kayo as a family (These days, we often sit next to each other, but we don't talk to each other. [I remember], we once ate at a restaurant with a large sign that says "Sorry, we don't have WI-FI here. We talk". And, I find it meaningful because you dine with your family."

According to a study on the impacts of parent mobile device use on parent-child interaction by Kildare and Middlemiss (2017), the use of mobile phones interrupts the time spent between a parent and child. Parents pay less attention to their children, which leads to weaker parent-child relationships. This is supported by Kushlev and Dunn (2019) stated that frequent use of mobile phones impaired the feelings of social connection and the meaning that parents derived when spending time with their children. Kushlev and Dunn (2019) stated that being online can harm our social lives. It minimizes face-to-face interactions and creates distance between humans without even realizing it.

Regular Basic Life Support (BLS) training for residents, especially PWDs

Some participants underlined the importance of basic life support training seminars, particularly for persons with disabilities (PWDs). P2 mentioned that even though they had received basic life support training, he reiterated that the community needs refresher training. As noticed, P11 showed interest by confirming the claims of P2. P11 said, "Kami as PWD kailangan na kailangan din namin ang Basic Life Support training kasi kami rin hindi rin namin alam kung paano i-handle yung ibang mga cases. Ma'am, kailangan din naming yun. P2 also recommended that one member per household should be trained in BLS, he said: "Ma'am, atsaka dapat daw bawat bahay dapat daw may isang marunong. (Ma'am, there should be at least one member who is knowledgeable (of BLS)). P6 shared that they want at least the fundamental knowledge of Basic Life Support, most especially on how to approach a patient, as well as what to look for before touching the patient. He also added, "Anya dagijay ti basic information nga dapat ammu mi. It's not the 3 days ngem nu adda ti shortcut na dagijay para ammu da ti aramiden da (What are the basic information that we should know? It doesn't have to be the 3 days (training), but if there's a shortcut to those things, so we know what to do."

The implementation of regular Basic Life Support (BLS) training for the community members is important in establishing an inclusive and prepared community, highlighting higher survival rates. Berlanga-Macias et al. (2023) emphasized that there is no training programs designed for people with disabilities but they can learn BLS skills. Physical disability is not an impeding factor to administer basic life support. According to Berlanga-Macias et al. (2023), physical disability was not a limiting factor, although it was a determining factor, in the teaching-learning process in BLS. Training should be flexible and tailored to the individuals.

Felt needs of the community members on the Peace and Order aspect

Sustained and Supported Peacekeeping Operations

The majority of the participants noted that increasing peace and order in their community is urgently needed, more so in protecting the youth. Participants raised concerns that some of the youths are spotted loitering in the Barangay during nighttime. P13 said, "sa peace and order, kailangan i-address natin, yung lalo na yung mga concerns namin is yung mga bata. Lalo yung mga minors na kailangan, hindi sila pagala gala dito sa mga national roads. Kailangan (uhm), yung ngay nasa bahay lang sila. Wag silang pa -gala gala. Yun din ang concern ng peace and order natin then yung..ang peace and order pa natin. (On peace and order, we need to address the concern regarding the youth, especially the minors. They should not be loitering along the highways. They should be staying at home. That's also one of our concerns." Participants also noted the strengthening of the barangay's roving patrols.

Barangay Tanods face challenges with habitual offenders among minors, while curfew and disciplinary measures are effective, intervention programs and counselling are needed to address the issue of minors (Bangit et al., 2025). According to Jabar et al. (2012), minors loiter around to release tension, boredom, go out with friends, family problems, and lack

recreational facilities around the community. These factors significantly contribute to social problems like vandalism and smoking at a young age. To worst, minors may adopt negative values if not addressed.

Conflict Resolution Seminar

Participants also bring to light the need for capacity-building programs, specifically on conflict resolution workshops at the barangay level. Being the frontliners, barangay officials are the first to experience issues in the community and are, therefore, knowledgeable on the basics of conflict resolution. P7 highlighted, “workshop on conflict resolution. Maganda yun. So, everybody will know how to solve a conflict. So, despite that, haan ka nga mastress. So, we need the resolution of conflict (Workshop on conflict resolution. That’s nice. So, everybody will know how to solve a conflict. So, despite that, you will not be stressed. So, we need the conflict resolution [seminar]).”

A participant also shared that, in conflict resolution, most of the cases that they have handled involve land disputes and collection of sums of money. P5 said, “Karamihan naman hindi na bumabalik dito. Except lang sa mga land issues. The majority of the cases (that we have handled) did not return here, except for the land issues.). She even mentioned that cases about land disputes cannot be resolved at the barangay level because they are not lawyers. P5 added, “Hindi, kasi ganto, tingin ko jan sa land disputes, di talaga namin kayang i-resolve yan kasi hindi naman kami legal. Pero kasi Ma’am, kailangan kasi bago magbigay ng CFA, kailangan daw kasi may initial confrontation yung respondent at yung complainant. Ang magagawa lang namin is to have them meet para lang magkaroon ng initial confrontation yung dalawa. Pagkatapos nun tama yung sinabi ni Sir na CFA na, kasi wala talga. Kahit bigyan pa kami ng dokumento, paano namin i-interpret iyon? During the interview, it was observed that participants who served as volunteers are in dire need of seminars related to conflict resolution. This implies that barangay officials shall have at least a basic knowledge about conflict resolution, most especially on matters involving land disputes. They added “Di naman kami lawyers. Kung mga simpleng encroachment, siguro kung mga simple lang. Kaya naman. Magjoint relocation survey lang sila, pwede. Kaya kami, obligado kami na we have to know something about law. Hindi ka pwedeng tatanga tanga jan pag naghahandle din. (We are not lawyers. If it is just a simple encroachment, maybe we can handle it. They can just do a joint relocation survey. That is why we are really obliged to know something about the law. You can’t afford to look ignorant in handling cases.”.

The case of the participants in this study is not isolated. These findings are backed up by recent studies like Laguda (2024) who explored the lived experiences of Lupong Tagapamayapa Chiefs in resolving barangay conflicts in Bacolod City, Negros Occidental. His study revealed that the Lupon Chiefs reported fulfillment in dispute resolution but faced barriers and desired more mediation training, particularly the older members of the Lupon. Participants highlighted the need to upskill in conflict resolution within their community. As Lupon Chiefs, the implementation of regular training helps in equipping them with the right tools and knowledge. Similarly, Araña et al. (2023) found that their respondents obtained a low score in the areas of conflict resolution, enforcement of rules, and legal procedures. This implies that a sustained training shall be implemented in the Barangay.

Challenges encountered by the community members on the Health aspect

Increasing Dengue Cases

Among the top concerns that the participants have identified is the dengue outbreak in the Barangay, which has affected the residents. P4 said, “Ma’am, may dengue outbreak ngayon dito. Kasama ang Pinsao Proper sa Top 20. Kahapon, Dalawa yung pinuntahan nila kagawad na bagong kakareport lang ni Health office dito sa Pinsao Proper. Pero mostly from Purok 1 (Ma’am, there is a dengue outbreak here. Pinsao Proper is among the Top 20 (with cases). Yesterday, there were two (2) individuals that Kagawad visited, which was communicated by the health office here in the Barangay.” In recent years, Barangay Pinsao proper has always been included among the Barangays in Baguio City with a high number of dengue cases. In March 2025, fogging was conducted in Pinsao Proper, confirming that the community is at high risk for dengue (Health Office Flags 3 Baguio Villages Due to Dengue Clustering, n.d.). This concern is not confined to this Barangay alone. Literature shows that dengue cases significantly affect the health care system of a community, putting a financial burden on both households and the government (Ladner et al., 2017).

Coughs and Colds.

Common illnesses such as cough and cold were also identified by the participants. P7 disclosed that coughs and colds are common for both children and elderly people. This is similar to the findings of Montecillo and Amparado (2015), who reported that colds, coughs, and influenza were the common illnesses experienced by the community members in Barangay Hipodromo, Cebu City. This implies an urgent need to sustain health preventive measures as well as community awareness to alleviate issues on this rising health concern.

Limited Access to Health Services

Participants also revealed that the barangay clinic has a wide scope of service. The clinic not only caters to Pinsao Proper but also to three (3) neighboring barangays - Pinsao Pilot, Guisad Central, and Pinget. As a result, medical supplies are not enough to cater to the needs of the people. P5 mentioned “Jay clinic gamin man, iccater na nga barangay, uppat. Pinsao proper, pinsao pilot, guisad central, ken pinget. Isu nga naglawla talaga ti iketcater na (The clinic caters four barangays: The Pinsao Proper, Pinsao Pilot, Guisad Central, and Pinget. It has a wide area of coverage to cater to)”. P5 also shares that when patients can no longer wait for their schedule at the barangay clinic, and they need to be urgently checked by a physician, people would voluntarily go outside.

Inadequate Supply of Medicine

On medical supplies, participants shared that even though maintenance medicines are available in the clinic, there are times when they run out of stock, and people have to wait for another batch of supplies. P9 said “Uhm, dagijay met agas, maintenance adda met, pero adda ngay jay times nga.. ti common lang nga adda is jay basic nga maintenance, amlodipine, yung pang high blood, nu awanen, awan ti stock, ag-uray manen ti supplies (Regarding medical supplies - medicines such as amlodipine for high blood are readily available but if it so happens that such medicines are out of stock, [they have to] wait for other supplies again)”. P4 nodded while saying, “Minsan nga mam, nauubos yung mga biogesics sa clinic.yung para sa cough and colds (Sometimes, Biogesics are out of stock)” and P7 confirmed when she said “They (clinic) have to give a prescription so we can buy outside”.

The insufficiency of medicine and limited access to health services may lead to increased morbidity and mortality. According to Nieva (2019), found that all municipalities in the Philippines encountered problems in accessibility and availability of essential medicines. This is strengthened by Carlo and Calucin et al. (2022), who studied the impact of medicine shortages and stockouts. His study revealed that shortages in medicines in hospitals and health facilities lead to adverse effects in patient healthcare. Naria-Maritana et al. (2020) emphasized that addressing challenges in primary care in the Philippines requires adequate human resources, facilities, supplies, and training for health workers and government leaders.

Waste Management and Proper Segregation Practices

Due to earlier restrictions on the disposal of biodegradable garbage, which confused, especially among renters and taxpayers, sanitation is still an issue. Community members still struggle with how to handle biodegradable materials, even though the General Services Office (GSO) eventually abolished the ban—organic disposal of wastes with some conditions (no feces or oil). P1 shared, “Ma’am. Maidagdag ko lang, dun sa... balik tayo nang konti sa sanitation. Kasi for a time, nagkaroon talaga kami ng problema sa basura. Kasi pinagbawal yung pagtapon ng mga nabubulok, syempre ang daming nagreklamo. Kasi they pay taxes. Isa yun sa..Kasama na dapat yun na service na binibigay ng government. Eh, di ba isa ’yon na pinagtalunan nang matagal kasi nga bawal magtapon. San sila magtatapon? Lalo na yung mga renters. Isa ’yon sa mga concerns talaga (Ma’am, if I may just add a bit—back to sanitation). For a time, we did have a garbage problem. People have complaints regarding the ban on the disposal of biodegradable waste. People weren’t allowed to throw away their waste, where are they going to put it? Especially the renters. Those were one of the major problems.”

Waste management and proper segregation practices in the Philippines are guided by Republic Act 9003, which mandates segregation at source, recycling, composting, and proper disposal to reduce environmental and health risks (Coracero et al., 2021). According to the 2023 Barangay Records Automation and Management System (BRAMS) report of Barangay Pinsao Proper, it revealed that 27% of the local constituents depend solely on garbage collection services of the city government, while 34.6% depend on both city collection services and composting.

The temporary restriction of the city government on biodegradable waste disposal shows dissatisfaction and confusion among the constituents, as many of them are confused about how to dispose of their waste. Others have resorted to composting, which involves turning leftover food—like rice—into fertilizer by placing it in containers. The BRAMS report shows that 4.7% of the community members are actively engaged in recycling and composting activities. P3 joyfully said while others agreed, “Ang na-oobserve po namin, Ma’am, yung mga kapitbahay namin, Ma’am, linalagay nila sa mga halaman. Ginagawa nilang compost na. Minsan kasi talagang strikto talaga ang collection of garbage. Kung minsan naman, kahit..uhm..linalagay nila sa pot, tapos linalagyan ng lupa para ma compost (We have observed Ma’am, our neighbors put their food waste in their plants and turn it into compost. Sometimes, garbage collection is really strict. So, sometimes, they put it into pots with soil to compost.”

The confusion among the constituents revealed that, without proper communication, even good policy can create resistance among people. This underscores an important lesson in public policy governance – policies shall be tailored to the lived experiences of the constituents.

Challenges Encountered by the Community Members on Peace and Order

Youth Violence

Participants identified a rising number of youth violence incidents in the Barangay. The majority of which include students who regularly fight and sometimes lead to a “rumble”. Accordingly, these incidents are not limited to a specific purok in the Barangay, but these youngsters brawl all over the Barangay. P2 mentioned, “Due to misunderstanding and arguments, students, ironically, often end up in rumbles. Not only here in Pinsao Proper, they get into brawls all over the barangay”. This finding is supported by Harumning and Sigalingging (2024), who found that intense rivalry between students, school egos, and student gangs are factors affecting violence between students. Macková et al. (2021) revealed that adolescents who experience family problems are more likely to engage in physical fights, with hopelessness acting as a mediator.

P2 continued, “Majority. Another thing is that in certain cases, Anger comes from jealousy. These conflicts are a result of bullying, cultural insensitivity, and bigotry, including sexism and racism”. P5 added weight to this observation, noting that “Ay oo alam mo mga bata ngayon magkatitigan lang. Suntuukan na ang kasunod niyan (Yes, Ma’am. Youngsters nowadays - just a mere simple stare-off, and the next thing you know, they’re already in a fist fight)”.

When the researchers delved further into the factors that the participants think can influence the bullying incidents. Accordingly, these incidents are caused by revenge and anger towards a person who has wronged them. P2 said, “Usually, it’s about revenge and anger. Towards a person who has wronged them. A form of disparity may be through physical, mental, or even something as simple as winning the game, misunderstanding, such as misunderstanding a person’s stature or capability.” P5 nodded and firmly said, “Topping it all, about family”.

In connection with this, some of the participants shared that there are only nine (9) Barangay Tanods deployed over the Barangay. P5 said, “Malaki ang ating area. And 9 lang yung ating tanod (We have a large area and we only have 9 Tanods)”. Curfews are implemented; however, there are still youngsters who keep on roaming inside the Barangay. Participants also noted the lack of functional CCTV added to the challenges in keeping the peace and order in the Barangay. Even when CCTV units are available, their effectiveness is limited by low visibility because of insufficient lighting, which limits their usage for gathering evidence during occurrences.

Anger is a strong emotion that arises from jealousy or envy. According to Behler et al. (2020), envy increases the motive of a person to harm and continue to behave harmfully toward others. Thus, it affects the said individual and his interpersonal relationships. Studies also explain why minors engage in harmful actions. According to Nechitaylo and Miloradova (2023), envy is not the sole cause of deviant behavior. Other factors also contribute to this phenomenon, such as inadequate social support, low self-esteem, and or negative environmental influences.

Cultural differences

The participants explained the complex nature of social dynamics present in the Brgy. Pinsao Proper about peace and order. As P5 pointed out, one contributory factor is that Baguio City is marked as a “melting pot” of various cultural traditions. She said, “Ang dami naming issues, Ma’am. Isang factor siguro din Ma’am, aminin natin na ang Baguio ay melting pot. Maraming nanggagaling from, you know, different regions and provinces, pag nagpunta na dito. Syempre nagkita kita, iba ibang kultura, yun. Isang factor yun. (We have a lot of issues, Ma’am. The fact that Baguio is a melting pot - this may be one of the factors. people from different provinces and regions come together here with different cultures.”.

These differences usually result in misunderstandings and clashes. P5 shared that these issues often stemmed from small issues. Usually, a clash between children. She shared her experience when one party threw stones at one’s window. She said “Kasi pag sa Kalinga ka pala, at nabato yung kahit po yung bintana lang, at may nagsabi po ng” agpulong ka nga dagos ijjay barangay at makipag ayos ka agad” kasi hindi pala maganda sa Kalinga na kapag nabasag yung bintana, may katapat yun. So kailangan makipag ayos ka agad (If a window is broken in Kalinga, for example, and someone tells you, “Go to the barangay straight away and settle things peacefully”. You see, in Kalinga, breaking a window is not taken lightly; there are consequences. For this reason, it's important to resolve the issue right away)”. As she continued remembering her experience, P2 shared an unfortunate issue that they have resolved, which is the issue of ‘Aswang’ - a mythical creature in Filipino folklore often associated with witchcraft.

P5 confirmed that there were complaints similar to that. She said, “Meron. Meron nga nun eh. Nagreklamo, may negreklamo. “Ano po yun, Ma’am? sabi ko”, “Eh kasi po irereklamo ko po yung kapitbahay ko, pinagbibintangan niya akong

mangkukulam.”, Ang sabi ko, “Eh hindi naman po albularyo si Kapitan (Yes, there was. One such case actually existed. A complaint was made. “What is it about, Ma’am?” I inquired. “But the Barangay Captain isn’t a faith healer.” She added, “I want to report my neighbor because they’re accusing me of being a witch.” These circumstances might seem insignificant, but this shows a deeper level of social tension. Such misunderstandings are not unusual in areas where individuals from many cultural backgrounds coexist in close quarters, and they frequently mirror the more general problems of mistrust and cultural fragmentation.

Not only do local cultural differences occur in Brgy. Pinsao Proper, but participants also highlighted the presence of foreign residents. P2 recalled an incident with a foreign national - a Male Iranian - who had recently arrived in the City. On his first day, he boarded a jeepney and politely paid the fee, but the other passenger simply told him to get off, telling him he didn’t belong there because he couldn’t speak Tagalog and wasn’t a Filipino. He narrated, “I remember there was an Arabic resident here, who came from Iran. And on his first day here, he is riding a jeepney. Then, he was paying and asked the driver. He was very orderly. Then came along this one person telling him to get out of the jeepney because he does not belong and doesn’t even know how to speak Tagalog. He’s not from the Philippines; therefore, he does not have the right to use the public utility”. This incident may be considered an isolated case, but it reveals an underlying problem in multicultural communities, especially when people are unfamiliar with one another’s cultures. This may also leave a long-lasting impression on foreigners visiting the city. Thus, this implies that community organizations, local government, and the academe shall start to promote intercultural awareness.

On the other hand, P5 pointed out how people from Manila admire the drivers of Baguio. P5 said, “On the contrary, mga taga manila, bilib na bilib sila sa mga drivers ng Baguio. Magagalang daw. Spokening dollar pa daw (laughing). At aware sila sa mga batas. Bihira yung mga bastos na drivers sa Baguio (On the contrary, people from Manila admire the drivers of Baguio. They are respectful. They can also speak English, and they are aware of the law. Rude drivers are rare in Baguio)”. P2 supported this by adding “not to mention we are law-abiding. Here, when you are using the pedestrian crossing, people will stop”.

Multicultural and diverse communities have both positive and negative implications for intergroup relations (Verkuyten & Yogeeswaran, 2020). Affinito et al. (2023) conducted a controlled experimental study on adults with multicultural experiences across multiple countries. Affinito et al. (2023) found that multicultural experiences can bring open-mindedness or the opposite. Accordingly, when people had bad experiences in a multicultural society, specifically with a certain culture, they became more prejudiced towards the group involved and even towards other unrelated minority groups. Negative experiences can change the way people think about others. The most fruitful strategy for mainstream cultural groups for maintaining harmonious intergroup relations in diverse societies might be that of optimal distinctiveness (Batkhina et al., 2022).

PINSAO PROJECT: A Proposed Sustainable Community Outreach Program for Barangay Pinsao Proper, focusing on Health Promotion and Enhancing Peace and Order

This sustainable community outreach program for Barangay Pinsao Proper is a response to pressing issues encountered by the Barangay regarding health, peace, and order. On the health aspect, this study highlights the inadequate medical services and supplies encountered by the Barangay. Mental health was also reported as a critical concern, especially among youth and solo parents. To address this, the researchers proposed a cluster of lectures on mental health awareness, including responsible parenthood and parent effectiveness, and the implementation of intervention programs such as fitness programs and others. Waste management and an increase in dengue cases are seen to be major issues in the barangay, which call for educational campaigns and sanitation drives. In terms of peace and order, the researchers have identified incidents of youth violence, misunderstandings among community members due to cultural differences, a lack of barangay patrol volunteers, and others. To this, the researchers have developed a three-year development plan to cater to the felt needs of the Barangay.

This program has three phases of implementation. As shown in Tables 1, 2, and 3. Year one is the implementation of programs related to foundation and awareness, year two is the implementation of programs and activities such as medical missions and others, and lastly, Year three is the implementation of programs and activities related to evaluation and sustainability (See Appendix A).

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study set out to assess the community needs of Barangay Pinsao Proper, Baguio City, with particular focus on health services and peace and order. Findings consistently revealed that residents prioritize three critical areas: the reliable availability of medical supplies, the institutionalization of seminar and counseling programs targeting both youth and adult populations, and the sustained operation of community-based peacekeeping initiatives. These results directly address the

research problem by confirming that unmet basic health and safety needs remain central barriers to community well-being in urban barangays. Notably, the depth of felt needs expressed by participants underscored a gap not only in resources but in structured, long-term community development planning — a finding that prompted the researchers to formulate a responsive three-year development plan in partnership with a local institution. Moving forward, this study contributes to a growing body of evidence that participatory community needs assessment is an essential foundation for sustainable local governance and grassroots development. Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. The Local Government of Baguio, in close coordination with the barangays, shall regularly monitor the availability of medicines in the City. Each barangay shall also establish an effective and efficient inventory system to prevent a shortage of medicines.
2. The Barangay shall implement sustained seminar workshops to empower Barangay volunteers. If possible, performance-based monetary compensation shall be given to them to recognize their dedication and efforts.
3. The University of Baguio shall integrate and implement the proposed development plan into the annual work plans of concerned schools and offices. The same development plan shall also be presented to the Barangay for their approval. Also, an impact study shall be conducted after the implementation of the three-year development plan.
4. For future researchers, a similar study shall be conducted focusing on how the presence of a culturally diverse community influences and contributes to the promotion of peace and order.

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Data Availability Statement

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study; all data used were obtained from previously published sources as cited in the reference list.

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Appendices

No appendices are attached to this study.